

Giant Phyllodes Sarcoma: Case Report

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INTRODUCTION

Malignant phyllodes tumor of the breast (MPTB) is a rare but distinct clinico-pathological entity representing <1% of all malignant tumors of the breast with an incidence of approximately 2.1 per million ^[1]. These tumors usually occur in women in the 4th or 5th decade of life. They can develop rapidly, and the associated symptoms can mimic other types of breast carcinoma, particularly if the mass ulcerates and bleeds. The bulk of this tumor is made up of connective tissue with mixed cystic and solid gelatinous areas ^[2]. Malignant tumors are usually rhabdomyosarcoma and liposarcoma rather than fibrosarcoma, and the number of mitoses may help in the diagnosis of the malignant subtype ^[3]. Surgery is the typical treatment of choice for MPTB, and radiotherapy is recommended for those at high risk of local recurrence. Chemotherapy is used to treat patients at high systemic metastatic risk ^[3]. The cut-off point for giant phyllodes tumor is 10 cm, this size presents management problems for the surgeon and given its rarity, decisions on treatment options are based on small-scale retrospective clinical trials or case reports. What was fascinating in our case was not just the initial presentation, but the aggressiveness of this phyllodes variation given bilaterality, recurrence and bone metastases.

CASE PRESENTATION

Patient S.F, aged 27 with pathological history: followed for a high-grade phyllodes tumour of the left breast since 2019 with a second recurrence in 2021 having had a left mastectomy + axillary curage at anapath: high-grade phyllodes tumour, 4 mm from the lower margin and remains distant from the others, 0N+/5N. Clinical examination revealed a bilobed mass covering the entire right breast, mobile in relation to both 2 planes, with no nipple discharge or inflammatory signs, and no axillary adenopathy (**Figure 1**).

Mammography reveals two voluminous masses distorting the mammary contours and occupying almost all the right internal quadrants. The larger mass is centred on the QSI, while the second is located in the QII, they are high in tone, well-defined, with regular contours (Figure 2).

On mammary ultrasound: two well-limited, rounded masses with discreetly irregular contours, hypoechoic and heterogeneous, the larger one with a few central cystic logettes measuring 88 x84 x81 mm and the other lesion in the right QII measuring 39 x37 x35 mm (Figure 3) classified as BIRADs 4 .

Une biopsie au tru-cut :tumeur fibro-épithéliale pouvant être en rapport avec une tumeur phyllode de haut grade. un bilan d'extension a objectivé une Lésions d'allure secondaire hépatique (nodule du segment VI de 9 x 8mm) et thoracique (nodule scissure gauche, sous pleural droit), broncho pneumopathie probable associée avec une probable localisation secondaire osseuse (lésion ostéolytique de la diaphyse fémorale droite) .

La patiente a eu une mastectomie droite et ganglion sentinelle. Les échantillons de biopsie et postopératoires ont été fixés par du formol, inclus dans de la paraffine, tranchés et colorés par de l'hématoxyline et de l'éosine . L'immunohistochimie a été réalisée à l'aide de la méthode dex-tran-polymère (EnVision+ ; Dako, Glostrup, Danemark) en utilisant les anticorps anti-humains monoclonaux de souris suivants contre Ki-67 , groupe de différenciation (CD)34 , desmine , antigène commun leucocytaire (LCA), actine musculaire lisse (SMA), récepteur des œstrogènes, S-100 , CD68 et cytokératine a révélé une tumeur phyllode maligne de haut grade avec nécrose multifocale La tumeur primaire mesurait 19 × 17 × 8 cm, sans atteinte de la peau ni des tissus sous le mamelon et du fascia superficiel, et un taux de mitose élevé avec signes d'invasion lymphovasculaire . Les résultats finaux d'immunohistochimie ont démontré un indice Ki-67 de 50% + ; réactivité négative pour la cytokératine, AE1/AE3, CD34, desmine, LCA, SMA et ER(-) ; et une réactivité positive diffuse pour S-100 et CD68. Les ganglions lymphatiques sentinelles 3N+/3N.

Figure 1: Breast appearance

Figure 2: mammographic appearance

Figure 3: Aspect échographique de la masse.

DISCUSSION

Phyllodes sarcomas are rather rare entities, representing only 1% of all breast tumors. In terms of etiology, Li-Fraumeni syndrome (TP53 germline mutation) has been reported to increase the risk of phyllodes tumors. These tumours often occur as a rapidly growing breast mass, considered giant if it exceeds 10cm in size ^[1]. Giant phyllodes sarcoma can lead to hypoglycemia, resulting from increased levels of insulin-like growth factor 2 produced by the tumor, and a high rate of metastasis in 6.2-25% of cases, most commonly to the lungs, bones and liver ^[4].

Mammography and breast ultrasound cannot differentiate phyllodes from other benign breast conditions such as fibroadenomas ^[5]. Fine-needle aspiration cytology or even tru-cut biopsy can establish the diagnosis, which will be confirmed after anathomopathological studies of the surgical specimen.

Surgery is the treatment of choice for phyllodes sarcoma. For years, the choice between breast-conserving surgery and mastectomy has remained controversial. Wide resection with clear margins of ≥ 1 cm has been recommended ^[6]. However, the study by Belkacémi et al found that total mastectomy was superior to conservative treatment in malignant phyllodes tumors in order to ensure adequate safety margins^[7]. Mituś et al argued that a tumor-free margin of ≥ 1 cm is essential for favorable local control after conservative or radical

surgery. Sarcoma has a rare propensity for axillary lymph node metastasis, described in <10% of cases; consequently, lymph node curage is not routinely performed [8].

Positive surgical margins, tumor size, high number of mitoses, stromal proliferation and necrosis are factors in poor prognosis and local recurrence. For patients with phyllodes sarcoma measuring > 2 cm after lumpectomy, or tumours > 10 cm after mastectomy, adjuvant radiotherapy is strongly recommended to control the high local relapse rate of $\geq 15\%$ despite healthy margins and reduce local recurrence, which is considered a strong indicator of distant metastases and associated with a significantly increased risk of mortality [9]. Radiotherapy is also an effective treatment for symptomatic phyllodes sarcoma metastases, especially bone metastases [10]. The role of adjuvant chemotherapy remains controversial; cisplatin and etoposide, and ifosfamide alone or in combination with doxorubicin are recommended for large tumors (> 5 cm) or recurrent tumors [11].

Our patient had several factors for a high probability of local recurrence and poor prognosis, including tumor size > 10 cm, high mitosis rate, poorly organized stroma with variable arrangement, marked pleomorphism, focal tumor necrosis. She received postoperative radiotherapy and adjuvant chemotherapy and is currently under strict surveillance.

CONCLUSION

One of the challenges facing the treating physician in phyllodes sarcoma is finding patients who will develop local recurrence or metastases. Surgical management is the mainstay of treatment, and local recurrence of phyllodes tumors has been associated with several risk factors, the most important of which is postoperative margins.

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